

This is the original submission and accepted manuscript of the article which has been recently published [First published Aug 21, 2024] as:

*Calvo-Maturana, C. (2024). A Mama for Owen: re-addressing adoption creatively in an accordion of visual parallelism. *Visual Communication*, 0(0).
<https://doi.org/10.1177/14703572241239491>*

*The published version - modified after peer review process and editing proofs- is available at
<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/14703572241239491>*

A Mama for Owen: Re-addressing adoption creatively in an accordion of visual parallelism

Coral Calvo-Maturana
Universidad de Granada

The paper critically explores the concept of ‘adoption’ via the semiotic analysis of the picture book *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2006), which stands here as a testimony of adoption narratives and ways in which they are creatively re-addressed in the context of children’s literature; as children books that challenge traditional stories, establishing a contrastive dialogue, are able “to sow and nurture the seeds of social change” (Reinolds 2011, 5). The study proposes the application of textual tools of analysis developed in the area of stylistics (Short 1996; Toolan 1998; Simpson 2004) to the examination of the visual mode. In particular, it suggests (partial) visual repetition, visual parallelism and “visualmetrics” as creative tools that are essential here in the process of meaning-making and re-assessment of adoption. The analysis of the visual mode is completed drawing on visual grammar (Kress and Van Leeuwen [1996] 2006; Painter 2009) and pictorial metaphors (Forceville 1996, 2006). The investigation identifies the semiotic choices at play and their multimodal display in terms of storytelling and narrative progression (Labov 1972) in an accordion like structure that results in the cognitive power of a work of art. The paper ultimately embraces picture books as enriching multimodal narratives which can build more inclusive communities, in this case celebrating the family unit beyond the genetic bond or gender roles.

Keywords: social semiotics, adoption, picture books, visual repetition, visual parallelism, multimodality

“Valued creativity originates in exploiting human propensity to pattern matching to draw readers’ attention and prompt them into thought in verbal as in other forms of art”
(Hall 2014: 92)

“[Picture books are] powerful ideological tools in their social function of “naturalizing” (or, less frequently, challenging) prevailing values about childhood, home and family.” (Painter 2009: 40)

Introduction

The opening quote highlights the cognitive power of parallelism to prompt human thinking and engagement (Hall 2014, 92), together with its applicability across arts; and consequently, across the semiotic affordances of each specific genre. This paper explores the role of visual parallelism and simple (partial) repetition as devices to convey meaning and (re)construct adoption narratives via the qualitative analysis of *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007), a picture book in which this tool is argued to be one of the main strategies to (re)address adoption, emphasizing care and affection as major indicators of family bonds. It thus illustrates the ideological and cultural value of picture books as specified in the second opening quote by Painter (2007, 40), who also underlines their pedagogical value in terms of (multimodal) literacy.

The study likewise aims at establishing a dialogue between stylistics and multimodality, measuring the extent to which stylisticians’ “toolkit” (Katie 2014) developed to provide an answer to the textual mode in the interpretation of literary texts, could well be applied to the discussion and understanding of other meaning-making modes such as the visual. The interplay of visual parallelism with narrative progression will be analysed making use of Labov (1972)’s taxonomy of components in storytelling. In this respect, the application of the scholar’s typology to a text of a multimodal nature will require reconsidering categories such as ‘evaluation’. The analysis will be completed drawing on Kress and Van Leeuwen’s visual grammar ([1996] 2006) as applied to the particular case of picture books (Painter 2009; Painter, Martin and Unsworth 2013, and Moya 2015) as well as Forceville’s framework of pictorial and

multimodal metaphors (Forceville 1996, 2006) in relation to picture books (Calvo-Maturana, 2020).

A Mama for Owen (Bauer and Butler 2007) is a non-fictional picture book based on the real story of Owen, a hippopotamus who was rescued by the Kenya Wildlife Service and local fishermen when he and his family were driven away by the floods of a tsunami. Owen was brought back by one of the waves but his mother was missing. As the author's note explains, making the reader aware of Owen's vulnerable situation, hippopotamus calves normally are in need of their mother for four years, but Owen was only nearly one year old. He was brought to the nature preserve "Haller Park" to be taken care of and there he chose Mzee, which means "Old man" in Swahili, a 130-year-old Aldabra male tortoise, as his mother.

Even though it could be understood as a non-fictional picture book, it does use devices to lessen the severity of the testimony and present a more friendly environment for children, the target readers/viewers, so that they can confront a testimony of loss and learn from Owen's resilience as well as from the enriched concept of "family" that Owen and Mzee represent. This balance between harshness and amiability is mentioned in other reviews addressing the picture book when alluding to the tsunami representation as "an effective yet not overwhelming scary sequence" (Wilson 2008, 77), or referring to the loss depicted 'delicately' (Reilly-Weiss 2009, 266). The analysis will thus try to identify those markers that are here understood as mitigators and helpers in the construction of the safe-space that the picture book signifies for children and adults to address complex concepts such as 'loss', 'identity', or 'belonging'.

As specified in *Kirkus Review* (2009), Owen's story was formerly represented in Winter's *Mama: A True Story* (2006) as well as Hatkoff et al's *Owen and Mzee* (2006), the former a picture book highlighted for its more intense dramatization and decreased role of the textual mode, the later for its photographic nature and narrative text; a book translated into more than 24 languages that sold over one million copies and resulted in a sequel in the following year (National Geographic 2023). Amongst other adaptations, the story also inspired a musical performed by *Vital Theatre* at New York's 'Actor Temple Theatre' in November 2021 in which parallelism of musical notes and lyrics 'love has a way of finding you' take part in the delivery of the message (Vital Theatre). Finally, Auerbach discusses a DVD adaption of *A Mama for Owen* and recommends teachers to use it as a "non-threatening version with young viewers dealing with loss or for units on Mother's Day, animals, or weather" (2008, 64). Within this quote, I would

like to highlight how the concept of “family” could be discussed along other central uses such as the environment, embracing the rich pedagogical input of the work.

The public interest of these two figures and their mutual affection can also be seen in the social media –*Instagram*- or the internet where their protagonist have their own official website and wikipedia entry. The news about their life story was likewise covered by the BBC (BBC News 2005), which reproduces tourism manager Kimoti’s voice acknowledging Mzee’s role as a mother to Owen. The news similarly refer to the activities the participants completed together such as sleeping or eating, or the way in which Owen followed Mzee and licked his face, which Bauer and Butler (2007) manage to imaginatively reproduce in their work in a clear case of multimodal intertextuality.¹

A critical insight to picture books is necessary as these narratives offer a safe space for children, whether having experienced adoption and foster care or not, to (re)shape their understanding of families. They can likewise function as conversation starters to address challenging issues of ‘otherness’. These are spaces in which children can construct their own identity, while at the same time understanding those around them, as “quality literature [the research refers to picture books in particular] provides a sociocultural context in which social issues can be examined and a means by which to explore the worlds of self and others” (Mattix and Crawford 2011, 319-320).

Following the introduction, this paper is divided into three main parts: stance, analysis, and conclusions. The first one offers a theoretical background to the tools that will be used in the analyse of the visual mode in *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007), the second part is a three-fold section specifically addressing the narrative structure, visual repetition, as well as visual parallelism, and the final section offers some conclusions about adoption creative narratives as well as the proposed method.

Stance: a dialogue across modes and areas of study

Originating in the context of formalists Jakobson and Mukařovský’s theory of ‘defamiliarization’ from the norm (Gavins 2014, 197), the notion of parallelism began to be applied in stylistics analysis of the literary text in the 1970s. Ronald Carter, in an interview that discusses the role of stylistics as a field of applied linguistics, highlights

¹ Though not mentioned in the picture book, the sanctuary aimed at placing Owen at a later stage with the female hippo Cleo, who lived on her own in another enclosure. This could well be a continuation for a next picture book on Owen’s lifestory.

that it is in this period that “stylisticians were exploring the nature of deviant discourse, patterns of parallelism and deviation in language considered to be literary” (Carter 2014, 84).

This paper departs from Toolan (1998) and Short (1996)’s approach to repetition and parallelism in the textual mode to discuss cases of visual simple (partial) repetition and visual parallelism. Toolan (1998) addresses simple repetition, i.e. examples of exact repetition of words, as a case of lexical cohesion and adds value on the role of repetition as a strategic tool to enhance meaning. As such, and even though it may occasionally be linked to a poorly constructed narrative, repetition is on the contrary very often a meaningful tool to underline ideas. Corpus linguistics studies, gathering data on the frequency of word-tokens as a salience indicator to be confronted in the interpretation of the text (Baker 2006, 47-68), corroborate the non-arbitrariness of repetition in the tailoring of a given discourse. Alluding to their salient nature, Short (1996) supports the simple repetition of words or bigger grammatical units as a means of foregrounding, and underlines parallelism as a more engaging method in which there are some features that remain unvaried, mainly of an structural nature, and some other aspects that diverge, normally of a lexical kind. When addressing parallelism, the scholar underscores what he calls “the parallelism rule”:

What is interesting about parallel structures, in addition to their perceptual prominence, is that they invite the reader to search for meaning connections between the parallel structures, in particular in terms of the parts which are varied [...] Thus parallelism has the power not just to foreground parts of a text for us, but also to make us look for parallel or contrastive meaning links between those parallel parts (Short 1996, 14-15).

Parallel structures thus act as triggers to (i) draw the addressee’s attention on themselves thanks to the similarity of the grammatical units, while at the same time (ii) sparking a meaning connection amongst the features that differ. There is thus a necessary connection between parallelism and effect, and analysing those patterns in detail can help uncovering meaning: “Great works do often contain stimulating sets of parallel linguistic features, and the explicit recognition and examination of patterning can lead a reader on to more significant findings” (Hall, 2014: 92).

(Partial) visual repetition and visual parallelism will be explored in relation to their role in the progression of the narrative, following Labov (1972)'s six fold taxonomy of narrative structure: abstract, orientation, evaluation, complicating action, resolution, and coda, as discussed in Simpson (2004) and Toolan (2006). The abstract refers to the essence of the story, what is the story about, whereas the orientation offers a background to the narration alluding to the participants, setting, and what had happened. While other categories in the narration may be omitted, such as in media res stories that skip the orientation, the complicating action seems to be a requirement in storytelling, i.e. a significant turn of events, which is normally followed, though not necessarily, by a resolution of that conflict and a coda or final morale. Especially complex is the category of evaluation that makes visible the viewpoint of narrators as either internal: "all kinds of highlighting and texturing devices, which can be thought of as added to the bare telling of the narrative clauses" (Toolan 2006, 61) or external: "the narrator stands outside the flow of the narrative to give an evaluation" (Toolan 2006, 60-61), together with the characters' viewpoint in those cases of embedded evaluation. Though the linguistic form in which these categories are conveyed has been explored, there seems to be the need to specify realisations of these narrative categories in modes other than the textual.

The visual mode will likewise be approached via Kress and van Leeuwen's [1996] (2006) framework of visual grammar, which measures the extent to which Halliday (1994, 2004)'s verbal model of interpersonal, ideational, and textual metafunctions could be applied to the visual mode; i.e. which are the semiotic affordances of the visual mode so as to construct meaning. As Painter highlights (2009: 41), a Hallidayan 'metafunctional' approach to modes other than the verbal evaluates how a given text functions so as to simultaneously convey three types of meaning: roles and attitudes, represented or emphasized ideas, and how these are arranged or linked.

In particular, and in answer to the corpus needs, the following areas of meaning-making will be discussed. In relation to representational meaning, this paper draws on Painter (2009)'s notions of 'activity sequence' and 'shift pace' to address the unfolding of a given action focusing on cases in which this is slowed down. Interactive meaning is in turn analysed through social distance, Painter (2009)'s framework of visual focalization, and visual modality; while compositional meaning is examined in terms of linking or the way in which different visual elements are connected. Visual focalization can be achieved through (i) either 'contact' or 'observe' images, addressing viewers or

just inviting them in allowing them to see, following Kress and Van Leeuwen [1996] (2006)'s notions of demand vs. observer looks; (ii) either directly or vicariously, as readers on the one hand, or as a character or along with a character on the other; (iii) either within a frame or across frames, in just one picture or a two pictures sequence. Moreover, if visual focalization is established vicariously along with a character, then there is the need of an 'observe' and 'within frame' scenario.

Finally, and as for pictorial metaphors, following Forceville (1996, 2006)'s taxonomy of contextual, hybrid, simile, integrated, and multimodal pictorial metaphors, the paper will draw attention on the creative uses of the simile subtype which arises from the contrastive similarities between a source domain and a target domain. The comparison is visually grounded via "juxtaposing target and source, by presenting them in the same form or posture, by depicting them with the same attention-drawing color or in the same (deviant) style, by lighting them identically ... - or by any combination of these" (Forceville 2016, 247), which encourages the mapping of characteristics from source to target.

The following sections combine these tools of analysis so as to respond to the process of meaning-making in *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007) and the way in which multimodal creativity acts as a vehicle to change and enrich our cognitive environment, in terms of our assumptions about adoption and families (Sperber and Wilson 1995), as well as aesthetically as a work of art.

Analysis

The analysis is divided into three main sections addressing the narrative progression and the accordion diagram, followed by the identification and discussion of the cases of visual (partial) repetition and visual parallelism, which are the basic tools in the process of meaning-making in *A Mama for Owen*. Textual markers are not discussed in this paper but it is essential to acknowledge their role, integrated with the visual, reinforcing the same connections via textual repetition and textual parallelism.

Playing the accordion: Multimodal application of Labov's narration categories

This section discusses the story progression in *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007) departing from Labov (1972)'s categories and in relation to the role of visual repetition and parallelism in the way the story unfolds. The analysis shows how the

arrangement of visuals displays the story as a type of accordion that encourages the reader/viewer to understand Mzee in terms of Owen’s Mama. *Table 1* shows in an iconographic way the accordion diagram. The narration categories in which it unfolds are identified vertically, while horizontally each row points at the relevant spreads, the specific part of the narration conveyed, and the cases of visual repetition and visual parallelism across the storyline, which specifically join the ‘bellows’ of the accordion. The picture book is analysed in terms of spreads rather than isolated pages as they are essential to analyse the whole canvas of the illustrator and its semiotic affordances.

	ABSTRACT	ORIENTATION	COMPLICATING ACTION	RESOLUTION
Book section	Front cover Inner folder Inner cover 1 Inner cover 2	S1, S2, S3l, S3r	S4, S5, S6, S7	S8l, S8r, S9, S10, S11, S12, S13, S14, inner back cover, inner back folder, backcover
Narration	(Front cover) Owen & Mzee (Inner folder) First pic of AS Owen spots Mzee (Inner cover 1) First pic of AS Owen & Mama playing hide-and-sick (Inner cover 2) Young Owen walking on his own	(S1) Owen’s family at Sabaki River (S2) Owen and Mama grazing (S3l) Owen and Mama playing (S3r) Owen and Mama lying together	(S4) Rain falling (S5) Owen in the sea roars for his mama. (S6) [Partial resolution] Owen is taken back to shore (S7) Owen in need of care looks for his mama and home	(S8l) AS resembling game hide-and-seek, Owen spots Mzee (S8r) Owen comforts himself next to Mzee (S9) Mzee comforts Owen (S10) Owen lays his head on Mzee’s back. (S11) Owen follows Mzee under the moonlight (S12) AS Owen and Mzee play hide-and-seek (S13) Owen waits for Mzee (S14) Owen smiles close to Mzee (inner backfolder) same as S8r (backcover) same as S11

(partial) repetition		Inner cover1 (p)- S31 (<i>Table 4</i>)		S14- Frontcover (<i>Table 2</i>) Inner folder - S81 (<i>Table 3</i>) Inner back cover(p)- S10 (<i>Table 5</i>) Backcover-S11 (<i>Table 6</i>)
Parallelism				S11-S2 (<i>Table 7</i>) S81 - S31 (<i>Table 8</i>) S12-S31 (<i>Table 8</i>) S10-S3r (<i>Table 9</i>) S3r-S14 (<i>Table 9</i>)

Table 1: Labov's categories in A Mama for Owen and accordion diagram.²

Note: Repetition and visual parallelism is tagged in the illustration that triggers the former.

The abstract of the story is presented in the front cover via the illustration that shows Owen and his new mama, the tortoise Mzee. The title of the book actually reads *A Mama for Owen*. This is a story about adoption, about parenthood, about protection, comfort, and care.

There are three more images that complete the abstract: the inner folder of the front cover and two subsequent inner covers (*Table 3* and *Table 4*). The first one shows the first illustration of the activity sequence in which Owen spots Mzee, a partial repetition of spread eight-left. In turn, the following inner covers respectively show the first illustration of the activity sequence in which Owen is playing hide-and-sick with his mama, partial repetition of spread three-left, and young Owen walking on his own. (Partial) repetition is thus a strategy used in the opening of the book to highlight bits of the storyline that are presented as wrapping up the essence of the narration: the time Owen enjoyed playing with his birth mother, only suggested but not depicted in the abstract, and the finding of his adoptive mother, the male tortoise Mzee.

The orientation of the storyline is developed from spread one to three, which present a panoramic mainly frontal horizontal view of Owen's family around the Sabaki River in Africa, favouring the engagement of the viewer (S1), Owen following his mama grazing under the moonlight (S2), Owen and his Mama playing hide-and-see

² Abbreviations used: S: spread, AS: action sequence, (p) partial repetition, l: left, r: right.

(S3l), and both of them lying together (S3r), answering to who, where, and what had happened in the narration. These illustrations are essential to understand the storyline because of the following visual parallelism with those that feature Owen and Mzee; a parallelism that catches the viewers' attention due to its similarity while at the same time encourages him/her to establish connections between those entities that change, describing Mzee in terms of Owen's Mama.

The challenging scenario that evolves in the complicating action could be considered to expand from spread four to spread seven; a series that opens with the rain falling over the Sabaki River (S4, *Image 1*), Owen alone in the sea roaring for his missing mama (S5), Owen being taken back to shore by a big wave (S6) and a confused and vulnerable Owen unsuccessfully looking for his mama and home (S7).

Figure 1 shows S4, the opening of the complicating action. Here, the drops of the rain over the Sabaki river are visually turned into words arranged vertically down the page in a list of coordinated clauses (1). Graphological deviation and iconicity thus reinforce the complicating action while at the same time visually displaying a barrier between Owen's life prior and after the rain; a barrier from which we could fold the narrative of this accordion, making the scenes featuring visual parallelism of both Owen and his mama, and Owen and Mzee, overlap. The monkey family on the left hand side showing carer and child holding each other in a relaxed attitude under the shelter of some tree leaves could work as a mitigating device to compensate for the severity of the subsequent events in the complicating action.

Figure 1: Opening spread of the complicating action © Bauer and Butler 2007

Locating the complicating action may depend on the individual reader's 'narrative 'antennae'' (Toolan 2006, 60); that is, which exactly is the moment that the reader understands as more challenging, as an intense or meaningful turn of events. Consequently, although S6 offers some partial resolution as the chance of a wave saves Owen from drowning, S7 (*Figure 2*), featuring Owen on his own, a child lost and lonely in the sea, could be said to stand as the peak of the complicating action. In terms of focalization, contact look may be understood as a claim for help, while the bird-eye view shows his loneliness in this new environment. The use of free indirect style (Short 1996) in the text draws us closer to him while at the same time highlighting his vulnerability: "*where was his mama?*"

Figure 2: Owen longs for his mama and birthplace (S7), © Bauer and Butler 2007

In turn, the resolution from S8 to S13 shows the activity sequence in which Owen spots Mzee for the first time (S8l) and snuggles next to him while Mzee soothes Owen to sleep (S8r, S9, S10), Owen following Mzee walking under the moonlight (S11), Owen playing hide-and-seek with Mzee (S12) and cuddling in comfort (S13). Owen and Mzee's bond is strengthened in the inner back cover, a (partial) repetition of S10 showing Mzee and Owen in frontal position cuddling, the inner folder of the back cover -repetition of S8r- and the back cover -repetition of S11. The extension of the resolution emphasizes the carer role of Mzee and Owen's comfort.

We can argue that visual parallelism is one of the most meaningful strategies to convey the coda of the story as by equalling Mzee and Owen's mama it lays emphasis

on parenthood beyond the genetic bond or gender roles, and underlines care, attention, and love as the defining characteristics of a family unit. As for evaluation, it will be addressed in the analysis of the following sections drawing on representational, interactional and compositional visual meaning, and specifically the examples of visual repetition and visual parallelism.

When exploring repetition, there is the need to consider both, aspects that are repeated and those that are not, as this is ultimately a matter of choice in the process of meaning-making. In this sense, none of the scenes of the complicating action are repeated, and are in this way downplayed, as well as “washed out” by the two halves of parent care in the storyline.

Visual (partial) repetition: embracing Owen’s life story from the love of his carers

All cases of visual simple (partial) repetition are located in either the opening front cover, and inner front cover and folder, or in the closing back cover, or inner back cover, enfolding the story. These are strategically used to invert the narrative and show the moment Owen finds his adoptive mama (a papa!), introduce Owen as the main protagonist, elicit activity sequences of quests of different nature, and foreground illustrations of Owen and Mzee that connect Mzee with Owen’s Mama by means of visual parallelism.

The first case of repetition is shown in the front cover that repeats the last illustration of the storyline, S14 (*Table 2*). This repetition is meaningful as (i) it visually wraps the essence of the storyline, the abstract (ii) it opens Owen’s life story from the comfort of the resolution, despite it later presents the anguish of being lost and alone and (iii) it stands as one of the pictures in a case of visual parallelism that points at the shared roles of Owen’s Mama and Mzee, discussed in the following section (*Table 9*).

Figure 3: Front Cover

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 4: S14

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 2: Owen smiles next to Mzee

In terms of social distance, the illustration shows a close-up of the characters which allows to introduce them in the opening of the book and draw the viewer closer to them, while at the same time enhancing their emotions. The close-up in S14, contrasts with other close-ups of Owen in the book such as S5 or S7 (*Figure 2*), showing a vulnerable Owen in need and in danger, either roaring for his lost mama in the open sea or troubled on his arrival to a new land on his own.

Owen life story takes the form of a life story book, a genre that originated in the 1970s in the context of adoption so as to strengthen the child's "sense of continuity and identity" and is, in more recent times, used as tools to address challenging experiences during infancy (Burnell 2009, 9; prologue in Rees 2009). Although the story in *A Mama for Owen* is presented in chronological order, the book cover already presents the protagonist in the comfort and closeness of his adoptive father, Mzee, anticipating a positive ending. This arrangement follows social worker Rees (2009)'s suggestion of an inverted order in the presentation of life story books so that children would learn about their life story from the safety of the adoption, which would then open other previous chapters, maybe of uneasiness. We could then refer to an inverted narrative via the use

of simple repetition in the front cover, which actually reproduces the last illustration in the narration, Owen finds a carer in Mzee who behaves as his Mama did and with whom he can relate or interact in the same manner.

There are two other moments in the narration that are highlighted in the inner folder of the book and the inner cover in cases of (partial) repetition with respectively S8L corner (*Table 3*) and S3left corner (*Table 4*). These are highlights in Owen’s life and could be discussed as adding to the abstract and the positive opening of the life story: a trigger of the moment Owen meets Mzee for the first time and a trigger of the hide-and-seek game Owen used to play with his Mama. Both cases could be analysed as either examples of simple repetition of the first illustration in the activity sequence or, alternatively, as cases of partial repetition of the first illustration in a three part activity sequence. This latter option seems more reasonable as probably the mere simple repetition of the first illustration cues the following, and it may not be arbitrary that the illustrator has chosen to repeat the opening of the sequence.

Figure 5: Inner front folder/(p)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 6: S8Lcorner

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 3: Partial repetition of activity sequence, Owen finds Mzee

Both scenarios in *Figure 6* (*Table 3*) and *Figure 8* (*Table 4*) are linked as in this storyline the quest for a parent is lessened by drawing a parallelism with the search in a hide-and-seek game. In this sense, the balancing of eye bird-view in the moment of search versus the close-up shots of the entities when being found is used on both occasions. The close-ups here are characterised by the physical intimacy of the participants and foreground their reciprocated comfort and affection. In *Figure 7*, the

choice of Owen emerging out of a bush hints on the one hand to the figure of his Mama and on the other offers a first portrayal and introduction to baby Owen happily playing in the context of his birth family that foregrounds in a tender way his childhood innocence. This is a humorous scene, a case of dramatic irony as the viewer uncovers Owen prior to his mother, and a potential mitigator to portray ‘loss’ in the story.

Figure 7: Inner front cover 1/(p)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 8: S3Lcorner

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 4: Partial repetition of activity sequence, Owen plays hide-and-seek with his mama.

The visual meaning in the back cover, both in the inner back cover (*Table 5*) and the backcover (*Table 6*), is conveyed through simple repetition of respectively S10 and S11 featuring Owen and Mzee in scenes that parallel those that depict the moments Owen used to spend with his Mama, in a paradigmatic visual choice that helps the viewer understand Mzee in terms of Owen’s Mama.

Figure 9: Inner back cover (p)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 10: S10

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 5: Partial repetition of Owen sleeping on Mzee broad's back

Table 5 shows a close-up (inner back cover) and eye-bird view (S10) of the same scene, the former emphasizing their physical intimacy and facial expression as a result of zooming in the participants, the latter showing the protagonists in the wider context of their environment, contrasting with the scene in S7 (Figure 2) in which Owen landed in this same environment on his own. There is a strong similarity between the photographs of the protagonists included in Hatkoff et al. 2006 and the illustrations in the picture book in terms of their physical resemblance and very importantly their position and ways of interacting, with Owen's face on Mzee's back or Owen licking Mzee; however, the picture book provides some distance from the real participants by lowering down the visual modality; i.e. how close to a true reality we believe the illustrations are.

Figure 11: Back cover

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 12: S11

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 6: Repetition of Owen following Mzee under the moonlight

Finally, the choice of back cover wraps up the story with a simple repetition of S11 in which the degree of closeness is lowered by reducing the format of the illustration and nonetheless framing it against a yellow background that can stand as an abstract representation of Owen's habitat. The relocation of the illustrations as well as the variance in visual co-text modifies its emphasis, while the back cover enhances the situation in itself due to the prominent position as well as the repetition and the framing of the illustration, S11 focuses attention on the figures and their physiognomy in a scene in which the moon is a spotlight drawing a "vector line" that illuminates both figures (Kress and Van Leeuwen [1996] 2006). The illustration echoes Owen's daily routine with his Mama, as will be discussed in the following section that presents meaning relations established through visual parallelism.

Visual parallelism: understanding Mzee in terms of Owen's mama

This section identifies the cases of visual parallelism in *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007) raising awareness on the meaning relations that result from the interplay of their similarity and divergence.

Table 7 shows the visual parallelism that links spreads 2 and 11, featuring Owen following his mamas under the moonlight. There are clear visual similarities running through both illustrations as both of them show Owen following his referent adult carer under a starry night and a full moonlight. The connections encourage us to understand Mzee in terms of Owen's Mama, and probably Owen's new home, the natural preserve in Haller Park, in terms of Owen's birth place, the Sabaki River. The arrangement, positioning of participants, or their "graying brown –or was she/he brownish gray?" colour favour the connection of both illustrations. The close camera shots in both scenes equally distributed in a full spread similarly take part in their likeness. In both cases, there is indeterminacy of whether these are examples of observe or contact look as the lateral depiction allows characters to have an either frontal or lateral view. Following Thornborrow discussion of syntagmatic and paradigmatic choices in textual parallelism (2006, 50-53), we could argue that in these illustrations there is a paradigmatic choice for either Owen's Mama or Mzee, which take part in the syntagmatic display of the picture. The position of the moon to the right or the left hand side of the participants may be an indicator of a temporal axis: past and present/future.

Figure 13: S2 © Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 14: S11

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 7: Visual parallelism, Owen and his mamas [S2-S11]

Following the discussion in Calvo-Maturana (2020, 296-302) in relation to simile pictorial metaphors in three adoption narratives: *A Mother for Choco* (Kasza 1992), *The Lamb-a-roo* (Kimpton 2006) and *The Little Green Goose* (Sansone 1999), we can argue that the visual parallelism encourages the simile pictorial metaphor: OWEN (HIPPO) IS MZEE (TORTOISE CARE-TAKER). In the former titles, and despite the narratives likewise aim at celebrating physical differences across family units, the pictorial simile worked in answer to frustrated former similes. As an example, the protagonist in *A Mother for Choco* (Kasza 1992) could not identify himself with Mrs. Giraffe, Mrs. Penguin or Mrs. Walrus since the three of them rejected him on the grounds of lack of physical alikeness, resulting in the frustrated similes: BIRD [CHOCO] IS (NOT) A GIRAFFE, BIRD [CHOCO] IS (NOT) A PENGUIN, or BIRD [CHOCO] IS (NOT) A WALRUS; an exclusion which is later re-addressed in the simile pictorial metaphor BIRD [CHOCO] IS BEAR when Mrs. Bear meets Choco and embraces their physical differences. In comparison with this contrastive relationship between frustrated and successful similes, in *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007), the pictorial simile OWEN (HIPPO) IS MZEE (TORTOISE CARE-TAKER) departs from a former successful simile OWEN (HIPPO) IS OWEN'S MOTHER (HIPPO CARE-TAKER) that shows that Owen can understand himself in terms of his referent care-taker even though they might not be fully alike.

The parallelism of the hide-and-seeK sequences as shown in *Table 8* is of major relevance as it delineates the metaphor THE JOURNEY OF SEARCH FOR BIRTH PARENTS IS A HIDE-AND-SEEK GAME in which the source is the hide-and-seeK game Owen used to play with his mama (S3, *Figure 15*) and the target is Owen's search for his mother (S8, *Figure 16*). This parallelism is strengthened in S12 (*Figure 17*) in which Owen literally plays hide-and-seeK with his new mama, male tortoise Mzee. This metaphor can be considered a mitigator to lessen the tough parts of the narration in which Owen, a calf, is positioned in a fragile situation. We can say that (S8) triggers back (S3) and (S12) in turn elicits back both (S8) and (S3).

Spread 3 shows the activity sequence in which Owen plays hide-and-seeK with his mama, the activity is slowed down into different parts, which diverge in terms of their interactive nature: (i-S3) Owen emerges from the tall grass: contact, direct and within frame; (ii-S3) Owen continues searching: observe, vicarious along with the character and within frame; (iii-S3) Owen finds his mama: observe, direct, within; (iv-S3) Owen snuggles next to her: observe/contact, direct, within. The interaction choices

encourage the participation of the reader/viewer who is called out in (i-S3) via a demand look, invited to participate in the search (ii-S3), and finally witness of the encounter (iii-S3) and invited to see as observer the intimate embracing of mother and calf, in which we may wonder if the mama is likewise looking at the viewer (iv-S3).

In terms of spread 8, the activity sequence unfolds in: (i-S8) Owen seems to find something (ii-S8) Owen approaches the newly depicted entity (iii-S8) Owen snuggles next to it. Even though Owen's vulnerability is enhanced by standing on his own in (i-S8), neither contacting the viewer nor depicted in a way in which the viewer could likewise take part in the game along with him, (ii-S8) echoes (iii-S3), and (iii-S8) echoes (iv-S3), tightening the overlapping of the target search for care-provider with the source hide-and-seek game. If we zoom in (iii-S3) and (ii-S8) to confront them in isolation we can see the strong visual parallelism of both scenes reinforcing the depiction of Owen's first encounter with Mzee as a hide-and-seek encounter. Even though the interaction options in (ii-S8) and (iii-S3) are shared: observe, direct, and within frame, these differ in (iii-S8) in contrast to (iv-S3) as this time Owen contacts the viewer while snuggling down next to Mzee for the first time, while Mzee who pleasantly sleeps keeps his eyes-closed in an otherwise contact view.

Figure 15: AS Owen plays hide-and-seek with his mama (S3) © Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 16: AS Owen finds Mzee for the first time (S8) © Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 17: Owen plays hide-and-peek with Mzee (S12) © Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 8: THE SEARCH FOR YOUR BIRTH PARENTS IS A HIDE-AND-SEEK GAME [S8-S3; S12-S8&S3]

Finally, S12 (Figure 17) links back to (S8-Figure 16) and (S3-Figure 15). The first aspect to highlight in contrast to (S8) and (S3) is that this is not an activity sequence but a 'list' of activities of the same nature – following Sinclair (1988)'s grammatics. These are: (i-S12) Owen finds Mzee slipping beneath the water, (ii-S12) Owen finds Mzee hidden amongst the grass, (iii-S12) Owen finds Mzee behind a rock. Moreover, all cases depicted are meaningfully the finding moments of the hide-and-peek game, in a way reinforcing the reassurance of Owen finding a care-giver. We can highlight the uplifting nature of the encounter in (i-S12) that shows the youth of the calf plugging into the water, the use of observe-direct-within interaction options in (i-S12)

and (ii-S12) in contrast with the observe-vicarious, along with character-within options in (iii-S12) which enable again the viewer to play along Owen, though in contrast to the other vicarious illustration of the hide-and-seek game (ii-S3), this time we do see Mzee in the background behind the rock. All scenes in S12 could likewise be understood as cases of dramatic irony since the viewer and Owen know in advance that Mzee has been uncovered. The uses of eye-bird view in (iii-S3), (ii-S8) and (i-S12), (ii-S12) and (iii-S12) is a pattern in all finding scenes, in contrast to the close-up shots of (iv-S3) and (iii-S8) of the moments of intimacy after they have found each other.

Figure 18: (S8r)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 19: (S14)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 20: (S10)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Figure 21: (S3r)

© Bauer and Butler 2007

Table 9: S8r, S10, S14 & S3r

All illustrations in *Table 9* stand out due to their compositional nature in which the two participants are connected in a positive physical intimacy that point at their attachment. Likewise, the close-shots of their faces contribute to corroborate that these are cases of positive physical intimacy that result in smiley faces, and sometimes closed-eyes of contentedness. In relation to social distance, the only illustration that differs is S10 offering a bird-view/zoom out shot of Owen and Mzee focalised by a vector line of the sunset, which enable the viewer to learn about Owen's new home. We can compare this illustration against spread 7 (*Figure 2*) in which Owen arrives to the same place on his own. There are thus three different illustrations depicting Owen and Mzee leaning on each other, a total of five adding the cases of repetition of S10 and 14, in answer and dialogue to the opening picture of Owen and his mama, emphasizing the role of Mzee as Owen's Mama. The variance in these visually parallel illustrations is the participant next to Owen, his mama and Mzee, who are here connected to be understood as Owen's care providers.

Conclusion

This paper contributes to the understanding of the narratives of adoption and the way in which families, parenthood, and care-providing is creatively and socially constructed. A critical insight on how these concepts are addressed is key as they are pillars of a person's identity and, specially in the genre of picture books, they take part in the child's construal of their persona. Moreover, following Toolan (2006), stories shed light and reflect the world that surrounds us, guiding us, providing focus and warmth, while at the same time echoing our understanding.

Narratives are lamps as well as mirrors, not merely representations of one's self and identity but explanatory representations of the world-of what is the case, and how things are. (Toolan 2006, 75)

In line with Kress and Van Leeuwen [1996] (2006)'s suggestion of a visual grammar, this paper ponders on the application of other textual frameworks to the analysis of the visuals, establishing a dialogue across modes and areas of study. In particular, it has explored the dialogue across models originated in the context of

stylistics and the textual mode and the analysis of the visual by discussing (partial) visual repetition and visual parallelism.

Visual parallelism has proved to be a key semiotic strategy in *A Mama for Owen* (Bauer and Butler 2007) so as to define Mzee in terms of Owen's biological mother, while offering an understanding of parenthood based on care, awareness, and affection that can confront or (re)address oppressive discourses that limit the concept to a genetic bond or physical likeness, or to the female participant omitting the male carer. It is the movement of the accordion that establishes connections between the first and second half of the storyline; that shapes the musical notes of Owen's life story and the one of his carers. There are degrees in the more or less likeness of the parallel visuals that ultimately trigger the meaning connection between those visual elements that diverge.

Similarity in these visual cases of parallelism has been identified in terms of the proximity of the entities, shared characteristics –e.g. colour, position- or similar contextual background – e.g. a full moonlight, or nature. The juxtaposition of Owen and his Mama or Owen and Mzee, as well as the joint features, encourage the mapping of Owen with both of his carers in a type of pictorial simile (Forceville 1996, 2006) in which OWEN (HIPPO) IS MZEE (TORTOISE CARE-TAKER), Owen can be understood as a member of the tortoise family. The simile pictorial metaphor is a strategy that is identified in Calvo-Maturana (2020) to re-address discourses of otherness in adoption narratives within picture books, and as such *A Mama for Owen* adds to the dialogue across this narrative and genre in the use of common visual semiotic strategies to redefine lack of physical resemblance as a feature to celebrate rather than resent in the context of family units.

Spreads that engage in visual parallelism are likewise foregrounded via (partial) repetition, which far from being arbitrary, is used to reinforce ideas, reverse the narrative, or trigger a larger sequence. The paper suggests the notion of 'partial' repetition for those examples in which the visuals are not fully repeated but which nonetheless could be argued to elicit the complete illustration or activity sequence. All cases of repetition were located within front and back covers, and added layers of meaning to the original by their relocation and change of "co-visuals".

The discussion of the narrative progression through Labov (1972)'s framework likewise entailed a revision of the categories from the lenses of the visual mode, specially to provide an answer to the 'evaluation' category. It is with this aim that the analysis of the visual mode has been completed via the expansion relations of the

activity sequences, the social distance and visual focalization, together with the framing compositional value (Kress and Van Leeuwen [1996] 2006, Painter 2009).

Close-ups are used to show emotions of vulnerability versus contentedness, highlighting via contrast the child's need of care and the protection provided by the carers: mama and Mzee. The eye-bird view is contrastively used as well to show either Owen's loneliness in an unknown environment or the company he finds in Mzee. In relation to the former, and following the metaphor THE JOURNEY OF SEARCH FOR BIRTH PARENTS IS A HIDE-AND-SEEK GAME, eye-bird view is used in the prior stages of hide-and-peek in contrast to the close-ups of those moments in which participants find each other and are connected in cases of positive physical intimacy.

Focalization is used to engage the reader in the process of search in the hide-and-peek game and the search for a mother, which is displayed in activity sequences that slow down the action, foregrounding the quest. As such, there is a case of contact focalization to catch the viewer's attention, just before the game starts, and a vicarious focalization to find Owen's mama along with him. Contact look was also present in the scene in which a fragile Owen lands in a new home on his own, requiring protection. An additional case was noticed in those illustrations in which the participants have their eyes closed in an otherwise contact look (Calvo and Forceville 2022), which are here related to moments of fulfillment. Hide-and-peek scenes in Owen and Mzee are depicted via a list of paradigmatic choices of finding, rather than activity sequences portraying the stages in the game, underlining Owen's success in his journey for a mama.

In line with the target audience of picture books, and their potential as safe-spaces in which adult carers and children can discuss challenging emotions or re-configure discourses of otherness, the analysis has identified several mitigating strategies that lessen the potential threatening aspects of the narrative by offering some distance from that reality while at the same time engaging in it: reversing the story in an inverted narrative that departs from a reassuring front cover that depicts Owen and Mzee cuddling together, featuring other animal companions such as the close-shot of the monkey family during the flood that washes Owen and his family away, the same choice of humanized animals as protagonists rather than children, lowering the visual modality through pastel colours, drawing on the cognitive power of novel conceptual metaphors to define the search, adding a humorous layer via dramatic irony, or making use of a lexical choice that adds layers of meaning of either a tender or humorous nature.

This paper has ultimately aimed at showing the cognitive power of picture books as works of art to re-address narratives and open new realities and spaces for children and adults, enriching our cognitive environment, embracing diversity, celebrating life. The visuals are here tools of expression, creation and freedom; tools for change.

Acknowledgements

I want to deeply thank the writer Marion Dane Bauer and illustrator John Butler of 'A mama for Owen' for generously granting me copyright permission to reproduce the text and image for the purposes of this research.

Disclosure statement

The authors report there are no competing interests to declare.

References

Primary sources

- Bauer, M. D. 2007. [J.Butler, illustrator] *A Mama for Owen*, London: Simon & Schuster Books for Young Readers.
- Kasza, K. 1992. *A mother for Choco*. Hemel Hempstead: Simon & Schuster. Young Books [1982, Japan: Saera Shobo; 1992, USA: Putnam's Sons].
- Kimpton, D. 2006. [R. Beardshaw, illustrator]. *The Lamb-a-roo*. London: Gullane Children's Books.
- Sansone, A. 1999. [illustrator, A. Marks; translator, J. Alison James]. *The Little Green Goose*. Great Britain: North-South Books. [Translated from 1999, *Das Grüne Küken*, Gossau Zürich: Nord-Süd Verlag AG]

Secondary Sources

- Auerback, B. 2008. *A Mama for Owen*. New York. Tomo 54, n°12 (Dec 2008): 64.
- Baker, P. 2006. *Using Corpora in Discourse Analysis*. London: Continuum.
- Burnell, A. 2009. *Prologue*. In J. Rees, *Life Story Books for Adopted Children. A Family Friendly Approach*. London and Philadelphia: Jessica Kingsley Publishers.

- Busse, B. 2014. "Genre". In *The Cambridge Handbook of Stylistics*, edited by P. Stockwell and S. Whiteley, 103-116. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Calvo-Maturana, C. 2020. "'Born from the heart': Social uses of pictorial and multimodal metaphors". In *Figurative Thought and Language Series*, edited by Hidalgo, L. and B. Kraljevic, 281-310. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Calvo-Maturana, C. and C. Forceville. 2022. "The Depiction of Family and Self in Children's Picture Books: A Corpus-Driven Exploration". In *A Multimodal Approach to Challenging Gender Stereotypes in Children's Picture Books*, edited by A.J. Moya-Guijarro and E. Ventola, chapter 12. London: Routledge.
- Carter, Ronald. 2014. "Stylistics as Applied Linguistics". In *The Cambridge Handbook of Stylistics*, edited by Peter Stockwell and Sara Whiteley, 77-86. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Forceville, C. 1996. *Pictorial Metaphor in Advertising*. London: Routledge.
- Forceville, C. 2006. "Non-verbal and multimodal metaphor in a cognitivist framework: agendas for research". In *Cognitive Linguistics: current applications and future perspectives*, edited by G. Kristiansen, M. Achard, R. Dirven and F. Ruiz de Mendoza Ibáñez, 379-402. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Gavins, J. 2014. "Defamiliarisation". In *The Cambridge Handbook of Stylistics*, edited by P. Stockwell and S. Whiteley, 196-211. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Jeffries, L. 1998. *Meaning in English. An Introduction to Language Study*. Hampshire: Palgrave, Macmillan.
- Katie, W. 2014. "The Stylistics Tool-Kit: methods and subdisciplines". In *The Cambridge Handbook of Stylistics*, edited by P. Stockwell and S. Whiteley, 32-45. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kirkus Review. 2007. *A Mama for Owen*, Austin, n°5, Mar 1, 2007.
- Kress, G. and T. Van Leeuwen [1996] 2006. *Reading Images. The Grammar of Visual Design*, London: Routledge.
- Hall, G. 2014. "Stylistics as Literary Criticism". In *The Cambridge Handbook of Stylistics*, edited by P. Stockwell and S. Whiteley, 87-100. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Halliday, M.A.K. [1985] 1994. *An Introduction to Functional Grammar*. London: Edward Arnold.

- Hatkoff, I., C. Hatkoff, and P. Kahumbu [Photographs by P. Greste] 2006. *Owen and Mzee. The True Story of a Remarkable Friendship*. New York: Scholastic Press.
- Hatkoff, I., C. Hatkoff, and P. Kahumbu [Photographs by P. Greste] 2007. *Owen and Mzee: Language of Friendship*. New York: Scholastic Press.
- Labov, W. 1972. *Language in the Inner City. Studies in the Black English Vernacular*. Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Mattix, A. A. and P.A. Crawford. 2011. "Connecting the Dots: Exploring Themes in Adoption Picturebooks", *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 39: 313-321.
- Moya Guijarro, A. J. 2014. *A Multimodal Analysis of Picture Books: A Systemic Functional Perspective*, Sheffield: Equinox.
- Painter, C. 2009. "Children's picture book narratives: Reading sequences of images". In *Advances in Language and Education*, edited by A. McCabe, M. O'Donnell and R. Whittaker, 40-59. London: Continuum.
- Painter, C., J. Martin and L. Unsworth 2013. *Reading Visual Narratives. Image Analysis of Children's Picture Books*. Sheffield: Equinox.
- Reilly-Weiss, H. N. 2009. "A Mama for Owen", *Childhood Education*; Olney, Tomo 85, n° 4 (summer 2009): 266.
- Reynolds, K. 2011. *Children's Literature. A very Short Introduction*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Rees, J. 2009. *Life Story Books for Adopted Children. A Family Friendly Approach*, London and Philadelphia: Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Sapir, E. 1929. "The Status of Linguistics as a Science". *Language*, 5: 207-214.
- Short, M. 1996. *Exploring the Language of Poems, Plays, and Prose*. United Kingdom: Pearson Education Limited.
- Sinclair, J. 1988. "Poetic discourse. A sample exercise". In *The Taming of the Text: Explorations in Language, Literature and Culture*, edited by W. Van Peer, 258-318. Londres: Routledge.
- Simpson, P. 2004. *Stylistics: a Resource Book for Students*. London: Routledge.
- Sperber, D. and D. Wilson. 1995. *Relevance: Communication and Cognition*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Thornborrow, J. 2006. "Poetic Language". In *The Art of English: Literary Creativity*, edited by S. Goodman and K. O'Halloran, ch.2. London and New York: The Open University and Palgrave Macmillan.
- Toolan, M. 1998. *Language in Literature: an Introduction to Stylistics*. London: Arnold.

- Toolan, M. 2006. "Telling Stories". In *The Art of English: everyday creativity*, edited by J. Maybin and J. Swann, 54-102. London: Macmillan.
- Whorf, B.L. 1940. "Science and Linguistics". *Technology Review*, 42: 229-231.
- Widdowson, H.G. 1975. *Stylistics and the Teaching of Literature*. London: Longman,
- Wilson, B. 2008. "A Mama for Owen" *The Booklist*, Chicago. *Tomo* 105, n° 4 (Oct 15, 2008): 77.
- Winter, J. 2006. "Mama: A True Story". Orlando: Harcourt.

Website references

- BBC News. Odd couple make friends in Kenya. January 6 2005. Accessed July, 25, 2023 <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/africa/4152447.stm>
- National Geographic Society "Paula Kahumbu harnesses the power of storytelling to inspire a new generation of conservationists". April 7 2023. Accessed July, 25, 2023
<https://www.nationalgeographic.com/impact/article/paula-kahumbu-explorer-story>
- Owen and Mzee music video. Accessed July, 25, 2023
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C1uAvwKJFNY>.
- Owen and Mzee. Official website. Accessed July, 25, 2023
<http://www.owenandmzee.com/omweb/>
- Vital Theatre Company. Accessed July, 25, 2023
<https://www.vitaltheatre.org/owenandmzee/>.